

INTRODUCTION OF MODERN RESOURCE-SAVING TECHNOLOGIES IN THE HEAT SUPPLY SYSTEMS IN THE CITIES OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN**Koroli M.,***PhD., Associate Professor**Tashkent State Technical University, Tashkent, The Republic of Uzbekistan***Hashimova F.,***Senior Lecturer**Tashkent State Technical University, Tashkent, The Republic of Uzbekistan***Ivanisova A.***Assistant**Tashkent State Technical University, Tashkent, The Republic of Uzbekistan*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7595334>**Abstract**

In recent years, a lot of work has been carried out in the republic to transfer the public utility sector to market relations. A legislative and regulatory framework has been created to regulate housing and communal relations, and market principles of management have been introduced. However, the existing problems and shortcomings in providing the population with uninterrupted and high-quality thermal energy, the inefficient use of energy resources in the production of thermal energy, excess losses during its transportation and consumption require the development of cardinal conceptual approaches.

The article presents the advantages and disadvantages in the schemes for connecting consumers to centralized heat supply systems in the cities of the republic. The reconstruction of the heat supply system of the cities of Uzbekistan has been rated, within the framework of the Project "Reconstruction of the centralized heating system and energy efficiency in the cities of Andijan, Chirchik, Bukhara, Samarkand and Tashkent (Heating Plant 8 (HP 8))" PRCHSEE. The scheme of linking heating systems and hot water supply of consumers to thermal networks according to a closed scheme is given.

The project is aimed at improving the energy efficiency and reliability of heat supply services, as well as the quality of heating and hot water supply.

Keywords: heat supply, thermal comfort, open systems, closed systems, connection schemes, independent heating system, open hot water supply system.

Introduction. The heat supply system is one of the most important components of residential and public buildings. Its main task is to provide thermal comfort for people in the premises. In Uzbekistan, a significant part of the housing stock, and almost all public buildings, are provided with heat and hot water using centralized systems. Great wear and tear of the main equipment and communications, incomplete provision of spare parts and materials, and often unsatisfactorily organized operation of heat supply systems - all this significantly reduces the efficiency of their use and largely negates their advantages. As for the heating systems of buildings and structures, their condition in most cases is simply deplorable - rusted pipes, increased hydraulic resistance, damaged fittings and insulation, and the absence of coolant flow metering devices.

An outdated, inefficient, misregulated system of production, distribution and consumption of heat inevitably entails a huge overconsumption of primary energy resources at heat sources, which is unacceptable in the face of rising energy prices. Increasing the efficiency of the heat supply system, therefore, is the main task in the reform of the public utilities [1].

Purpose of the work. Show opportunities to improve energy efficiency and reliability of heat supply services, as well as the quality of heating and hot water supply systems (DHW systems).

The problem. In open systems (compared to closed ones), there is a higher wear of pipelines and intensive scale deposits on pipes in heating systems of consumers, which worsens heating in apartments. Low-cost during installation, but expensive to operate, such systems are characterized by short service life of the internal heating system and pipelines of heating networks, high operating costs in the production, transportation and consumption of heat, excess consumption of network water and, accordingly, thermal energy.

Most of the main equipment in the field of thermal energy production is physically and morally outdated. The wear of boiler equipment is 70-100%, up to 65% of heating networks require major reconstruction, the efficiency of outdated boilers is low (75%), and the actual efficiency is up to 68%, which leads to a significant waste of fuel and maintenance costs. Open heat supply systems (Pic. 1) are systems in which hot water intake for the needs of the consumer directly from the heating network.

*Pic.1 Direct connection of the hot water supply system (open circuit) and heating to heating networks:
1 - sump; 2 – mixed water temperature controller; 3 – controller temperature sensor; 4 - water-folding riser;
5 – circulating pipeline; 6 - elevator of the heating system.*

In this case, the water intake can be partial or complete. The hot water remaining in the system is used for heating and ventilation. The water consumption in the heating network is compensated by the additional amount of water supplied to the heating network. The main advantage of the open heating system is its economic benefit. There are several disadvantages to such a system. First of all, it is the low sanitary and hygienic quality of water. The heating devices, pipeline networks give color, smell to water, various impurities, bacteria appear. Various methods are used to purify water in the open system, but their use reduces the economic effect [2,3].

In this regard, it is proposed in the public sector of the republic to use closed systems of centralized heat supply: heating the coolant through the heat exchange device of the heating point of the house from the boiler room.

With closed systems, corrosion control is easier due to higher water quality and lower volumes. The main effect of switching to closed DHW systems is an increase in the service life of the district heating system and related equipment, in this case, supply, distribution and pipelines inside the building. In addition, the quality of water in the DHW system is improved.

This will stop unauthorized selection of large volumes of hot water by unscrupulous consumers by establishing accounting in houses and equipping each apartment with adjustable thermostats in the future.

Closed heat supply systems - systems in which the water circulating in the pipeline is used only as a heat carrier, and is not taken from the heating network to provide hot water. The system in this case is completely closed from the environment. Of course, in such system, a slight leakage of the coolant is also possible. Water losses are replenished automatically by the make-up regulator.

The heat supply in the closed heat supply system is centrally regulated, while the amount of heat carrier (water) in the system remains unchanged, and the heat

consumption depends on the temperature of the circulating heat carrier. In closed heat supply systems, as a rule, the capabilities of heat points are used. They receive the coolant from the heat supplier (CHP, for example), and the central heating points of the districts regulate the temperature of the coolant to the required value for the needs of heating and hot water supply, and distribute it to the consumer.

The advantages of the closed heat supply system are high quality of hot water supply and energy saving effect. The disadvantage is the complexity of water treatment due to the remoteness of heat points from each other [2,3].

It can be concluded that, as classical schemes for connecting heating and hot water systems to heating networks, which are used in Tashkent and other cities of the republic, they have serious drawbacks. In this connection, it becomes necessary to improve the schemes of the heat supply system of the cities of the republic for the connection of heating and DHW.

The problem's solution. In accordance with the Decree of the Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 306 “On measures for the implementation of the project “Reconstruction of the district heating system and energy efficiency in the cities of Andijan, Chirchik, Bukhara, Samarkand and Tashkent (The main goal of the project is HP 8)” dated April 12, 2019 [4, 5], during 2019–2024, a phased transition of district heating to a closed system is being carried out in Uzbekistan, taking into account the introduction of modern resource-saving technologies, as well as an automated accounting system for the production and consumption of thermal energy and hot water at all stages of the production process. The project is aimed at improving the energy efficiency and reliability of heat supply services, as well as the quality of heating and hot water supply, providing for the modernization and reconstruction of central boiler houses, heat supply with a transition to a closed heat supply system.

As part of the pilot projects, it was decided to modernize the «Vodnik» and «Sanoatenergo» boiler houses in the Bektemir and Sergeli districts of Tashkent and transfer 118 apartment buildings and 43 social facilities to a closed heating system. The energy efficiency of modernization and reconstruction of the heat supply system can be shown by the following figures: if the current system is maintained, by January 1, 2028, accounts payable will increase to 14.4 trillion soums, and heat losses by 2030 are estimated at 5 million Gcal (44%), and the Veolia project involves reducing these figures to 1.8 trillion soums and 1.8 million Gcal (20%). It is proposed to modernize 181 boiler houses, install 28,000 heating points, reconstruct 841.1 km of existing networks and lay 575.6 km of new networks based on pipes with polymer insulation and a protective sheath.

In this paper, the authors present a heat supply project for a typical 32-apartment residential building, the connection of heating and hot water supply systems is carried out according to a closed scheme, where the heat carrier is heated through the heat exchange device of the heat point of the house from the boiler room. The calculation part is made in accordance with the following regulatory documents KMK 2-04-05-97*, ShNK 2-08-01-05 and for an area with an outside air temperature of -16 °C. Heat supply is made with the installation of an individual heat point. Individual heating points are supplied as a set and are installed in the basement

of a residential building measuring 2.4m by 4.0m. The individual heating point consists of a heating heat exchanger, a hot water supply system (DHW) heat exchanger - single-stage, a DHW regulator, a heating system circulation pump, a DHW circulation pump, heating system heat meters, a DHW flow meter. Controllers for heating and hot water systems are installed in the individual substation and must be interconnected so that “DHW Priority” can be used. “DHW priority” in this sense means the operation of the control system in such a way that, during peak hours of hot water demand, priority is given to the control of the DHW control valve. The heating system controller must be able to limit the temperature in the heating network return according to the measurements from the respective temperature sensor and using a reprogrammable algorithm. The controller of the DHW system must be able to set the parameters of the control algorithm by the user. The reconstructed boiler house of the microdistrict serves as the source of heat supply. The designed heating networks serve as the connection point. The heat carrier of the centralized heat supply is water t delivery -120 °C, t return-70 °C. The heat carrier of the heating system is water t delivery -95 °C, t return -65 °C. The heat carrier of the DHW system t-55 °C [6,7].

Picture 2 below shows the scheme for connecting a residential building to heating networks according to the closed scheme through an individual heating point.

Pic.2 Scheme for connecting a residential building to heating networks according to the closed scheme through an individual heating point.

Conclusion. The gradual transition of district heating to the closed system will bring social and economic benefits from investments in modern and efficient heat supply systems that will increase the reliability, safety and quality of services for the relevant population in the participating cities, (accounts payable under the current heat supply system of 14.4 trillion sums will decrease from to 1.8 trillion sums).

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6. Subproject: Chirchik city / Part 1: Chirchik city, Modernization of the Yubileynaya boiler house and replacement of 2 km of heating networks in Lot11 March 2022.